

LICENCING RESEARCH DATA: ADP's Experience

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Outline

I will be talking about

- Reasons for licensing research data
- Processes in ADP
- Creative Commons licences

Why license research data?

The open data argument

- To allow the data to be used in new ways: comparative studies, data mining, interdisciplinary studies, 'citizen science'.
- To permit greater scrutiny of research
- To raise standards of documentation
- To protect researchers from challenges
- To accelerate community-wide learning from experience
- To increase efficiency
- To increase impact

The pragmatic argument

- To provide clarity

Alex Ball, DCC, 2011

Data flow in ADP

DATA FLOW

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Share Alike		Yup, AND they must license the new work under a Share Alike license.	
No Derivatives			
Non-Commercial		Yup, AND the new work must be non-commercial, but it can be under any non-commercial license.	
Non-Commercial Share Alike		Yup, AND they must license the new work under a Non-Commercial Share Alike license.	
Non-Commercial No Derivatives			

License Agreement in ADP

- **Depositor** (name, institution, position)
- Name of the **survey**

- **Confidentiality** agreement / own copy
- **Copyright (CC + _____)**
- **Terms of Use** in order to protect the confidentiality of data

Enters into force when **both parties** (could be more than 1 depositor) sign the agreement.

Attached – list of deposited materials.

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Panton Principles

Principles for Open Data in Science

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Principles for Open Data in Science

Science is based on building on, reusing and openly criticising the published body of scientific knowledge.

For science to effectively function, and for society to reap the full benefits from scientific endeavours, it is crucial that science data be made **open**.